

Resistance^a of rice varieties to sheath blotch in Kaul, India.

Lesion length (mm)	Group	Variety
10-15	1	IET7662, IET7738, IET7753, IR13420-6-3-3-1, IR17494-32-1-1-3-3, RP2151-21-1, RP2151-33-4, RP2151-7752, RP2240-86-84, CN758-1-1-1, UPR80-149.
15-30	2	Jaya, Ratna, HKR101, HAU3800-1, HAU3855-1, RP1832-23-34, RP2151-27-1.
30-45	3	HAU101-88, RP2151-76-1.
45-60	4	HAU47-6045-1, HAU101-60.
>60	5	IET7641, IR19661-23-3-2-2.

^a Resistant = groups 1 and 2, moderately resistant = group 3, susceptible = groups 4 and 5.

ricefields in Haryana. The disease appears as irregular and brownish lesions that enlarge and become sepia-colored. The middle portion of the lesion finally turns whitish and is studded with pycnidia, the characteristic symptom of the disease.

We conducted a roving survey 15-18 Oct 1986, when the rice crop was at the dough to maturity stage. Disease incidence was recorded on both sides of the road every 8 km. Of 52 villages, in Ambala, Jind, Karnal, and Kurukshetra districts, disease was found in 11 villages, more in Kurukshetra than in other districts. No disease was found in

Hisar and Sirsa districts. Disease incidence was higher on rice variety PR107, followed by Jaya, Basmati, and PR106.

Incidence on varieties or genotypes grown under field conditions at Haryana Agricultural University Rice Research Station, Kaul, was measured during 1986 wet season. Those varieties were categorized into five groupings on the basis of lesion length on the outer leaf sheath. Entries with lesion lengths 1-30 mm were categorized as resistant; 30-45 mm, moderately resistant; and more than 45 mm, susceptible (see table). □

Insect resistance

Registration of brown planthopper (BPH)-resistant germplasm lines in Japan

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Breeding to introduce the BPH resistance gene from indica to japonica rice varieties started in 1968. Since then, we have developed four japonica type lines, each with one of four different resistance genes (*Bph 1*, *bph 2*, *Bph 3*, and *bph 4*) (see table).

Norin PL 3, with the *Bph 1* gene, was selected from the cross F₆ 324/ Akitsuho // Tsukushibare. F₆ 324 is the donor parent, with *Bph 1* from Hoyoku/ Mudgo/2/ Kochikaze/3/ IR781-1-94/4/Hoyoku. In 1984, Norin PL 3 was registered as a germplasm line by the Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry, and Fisheries (MAFF), Japan.

Norin PL 4 inherited *bph 2* from IRI 154-243 through the cross combination of Asominori/ IRI 154-2431 / 2*Asominori. It was registered in 1985.

Norin PL 7 from the cross Tsukushibare *2/ Babawee inherited *bph*

Germplasm lines with BPH resistance.

Line	Resistance gene	Donor parent	Days to heading	Culm length (cm)
Norin PL 3	<i>Bph 1</i>	Mudgo	128	71
Norin PL 4	<i>bph 2</i>	IR1154-243	128	67
Norin PL 7	<i>bph 4</i>	Babawee	127	83
Norin PL 10	<i>Bph 3</i>	Rathu Heenati	131	80
Tsukushibare	—	—	130	73
Asominori	—	—	130	76

4 from Babawee. It was registered in 1987.

Norin PL 10, selected from the cross Tsukushibare/3/Tsukushibare*3/ Rathu Heenati /Tsukushibare, inherited *Bph 3* from Rathu Heenati. It was registered in 1988.

The antibiosis of these lines to BPH is similar to or slightly weaker than that of the donor indica varieties. The lines show inhibitory effect on BPH survival and population increase and different reactions to the biotypes.

Their morphological characteristics are mostly those of japonica varieties, except for a few traits, such as the amylose content of Norin PL 10.

When these lines are crossed with other japonica varieties, the F₁ does not show hybrid sterility, except with Norin PL 7. Partial seed sterility was observed in F₁ plants of Norin PL 7/a Japanese line.

These four lines are being used to breed BPH-resistant varieties in Japan. □

Rice resistance to whitebacked planthopper (WBPH) *Sogatella furcifera* in Bangladesh

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WBPH incidence has increased in recent years, particularly in the irrigated boro (Dec-Mar) crop. We screened BRRI varieties BR1-BR12 and BR14-BR21 and 22 IR varieties, using the standard seedbox test. TN1 was the susceptible check.

Seedlings (20/ 12-cm row) were infested with 2d- and 3d-instar nymphs